

Variance of a difference between variables

The variance of variables x and y of respective means $\bar{x}$ and $\bar{y}$, in a sample of size N , are:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma^2(x) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \\ \sigma^2(y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2 \end{cases}$$

Consequently, the variance of the difference $x-y$ is:

$$\sigma^2(x - y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (x_i - y_i - \bar{x} + \bar{y})^2$$

Since the average of a sum is necessarily the sum of averages, we can write:

$$\sigma^2(x - y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i [(x_i - \bar{x}) - (y_i - \bar{y})]^2$$

⇔

$$\sigma^2(x - y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i [(x_i - \bar{x})^2 + (y_i - \bar{y})^2 - 2(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})]$$

⇔

$$\sigma^2(x - y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2 + \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2 - 2 \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})$$

⇔

$$\sigma^2(x - y) = \sigma^2(x) + \sigma^2(y) - 2 \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_i x_i y_i - \frac{1}{N} \sum_i x_i \bar{y} - \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \bar{x} y_i + \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \bar{x} \bar{y} \right)$$

⇔

$$\sigma^2(x - y) = \sigma^2(x) + \sigma^2(y) - 2 \left(\bar{x} \bar{y} - \bar{y} \frac{1}{N} \sum_i x_i - \bar{x} \frac{1}{N} \sum_i y_i + \bar{x} \bar{y} \right)$$

⇔

$$\sigma^2(x - y) = \sigma^2(x) + \sigma^2(y) - 2(\bar{x} \bar{y} - \bar{y} \bar{x} - \bar{x} \bar{y} + \bar{x} \bar{y})$$

⇔

$$\sigma^2(x - y) = \sigma^2(x) + \sigma^2(y)$$

QED